

Clinical Study of Patients Presenting with Acute Altered SensoriumMeet Patel¹, Prakruti Patel², Rushi Patel³¹Third Year Resident of Department Of Emergency Medicine, GCS MCHRC Hospital, Ahmedabad²Assistant Professor, Department of Emergency Medicine, SVPIMSR Hospital, Ahmedabad³Assistant Professor, Department of Emergency Medicine, GCS MCHRC Hospital, Ahmedabad

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Meet Patel

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Altered sensorium poses a significant and challenging diagnostic task for emergency physicians in managing patients promptly. Non-traumatic causes of altered mental status are diverse and require comprehensive clinical knowledge for effective management in the emergency room (ER), aiming to reduce morbidity and mortality. Therefore, understanding the clinical profile, triaging, treatment, and outcomes is crucial to optimize ER resources, especially in settings with limited resources.

Objective: This study aimed to investigate the clinical profile, emergency management, and outcomes of patients presenting with altered sensorium.

Materials and Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted on 50 patients who presented with acute altered mental status in the ER of a tertiary care hospital in western India between July 2023 and December 2023. Details of clinical presentation, management, and outcomes were recorded using a standardized form. Data analysis was performed using IBM SPSS version 26.0.

Results: The mean age of the study population was 59.88 ± 16.65 years, with the majority being over 60 years old, and males comprising 62%. Among the 50 patients, 27 (54%) had non-neurological causes contributing to altered mental status. The most common factor leading to altered mental status was cerebral vascular accident (CVA), accounting for 32% of cases. The study observed a mortality rate of 38%, with a mean length of stay (LOS) in the ICU of 4.26 days.

Conclusion: The study revealed a higher incidence of altered mental status among older adults, with a predominance of males. Non-neurological causes were more prevalent than primary neurological causes, although CVA was the leading neurological cause identified. These findings underscore the importance of early recognition, comprehensive assessment, and prompt management of altered sensorium in the ER to improve patient outcomes.

Keywords: Altered mental status (AMS), neurological, non-neurological, Emergency Room (ER).

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Introduction

Altered Mental Status (AMS) refers to any deviation from an individual's usual level of alertness, awareness, or cognitive functioning, often indicating an underlying medical condition [2]. It can manifest as confusion, agitation, memory problems, or difficulty focusing. [1]

Patients frequently present with unclear medical histories, posing significant challenges for emergency physicians in diagnosis and treatment. To improve diagnosis rates and treatment accuracy, a thorough understanding of the pathophysiology of AMS and comprehensive patient assessment are essential.

AMS can stem from primary diseases of the central nervous system (CNS) or secondary events affecting the CNS. Based on duration, AMS is broadly categorized as acute (symptoms lasting <48 hours)

or chronic (symptoms persisting >1 week) [1]. Chronic AMS is commonly linked to dementia and Alzheimer's disease, while trauma, infections, toxicological, and metabolic factors are significant in acute cases. [3,4] Neurological causes, and organ failure are more prevalent among elderly patients, whereas trauma and toxicological causes are more common in younger individuals. [6,7]

AMS is associated with extended hospitalization and high mortality rates, highlighting the critical need for efficient resource allocation in triaging, investigating, and treating these patients in the ER. Given the geographical variation in AMS causes, emergency physicians benefit from up-to-date knowledge of common aetiologies and available diagnostic tools for effective patient management.

Understanding regional AMS patterns aids in tailored treatment and care strategies.

Thus, this study aimed to profile patients presenting with acute AMS, focusing on their clinical management and outcomes.

Research Methodology: A prospective observational study was conducted on 50 patients with altered mental status who presented at a tertiary care hospital over a six-month period. The Glasgow Coma Scale criteria were used to evaluate the neurological condition of the patients.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Glasgow coma score <15
2. Age >18 years
3. Onset of symptoms <48 hours
4. Willing to participate in study

Exclusion Criteria

1. Age <18 years
2. Pregnant women
3. Patient with trauma, psychiatric, behavioral and chronic neurocognitive disorders
4. Onset of symptoms >48 hours

Statistical Analysis

A total of 4800 emergency patients presented to the ER during a six-month study period from July 2023 to December 2023, resulting in a prevalence rate of 2.095% for both acute and chronic altered sensorium. From this population, 50 patients with acute altered sensorium were selected based on predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Data were entered into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet (Microsoft Corporation, 2007, Washington, US) and analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY).

Results

In the current study, 42% of patients belonged to the age group <60 years, while 58% were aged >60 years. Patients with a Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score <15 were included in the study, categorized into three groups based on their scores: <8 (28%), 9-13 (56%), and >13 (16%).

In the present study, patients were categorized based on their diagnosis into neurological and non-neurological groups. Of the total patients, 46% had neurological diseases, with cerebral vascular accident (CVA) being the most common neurological cause, accounting for 32%. Non-neurological diseases constituted 54% of the patient cohort, with hepatic encephalopathy identified as the most frequent non-neurological cause at 18%.

In the present study, there was a significant association between Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score and the type of patient disposition (Chi-square: 9.69, $p = 0.008$). Specifically, 70% of patients with lower GCS scores required admission to the Intensive Care Unit (ICU), while 30% were admitted to the general ward. Conversely, patients with higher GCS scores had a lower likelihood of ICU admission. Notably, two patients with hypoglycaemia and a GCS score of <8 were initially admitted to the ward but showed improvement after initial treatment.

Table: 1 Demographic Characteristic of patients

		Frequency/Mean \pm SD at 95% CI	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	31	62
	Female	19	38
Age	<60 years	21	42
	>60 years	29	58
Mean Age	59.88 \pm 16.48		
GCS	<8	14	28
	9-13	28	56
	>13	8	16

Table: 2 Neurological and Non-neurological disease.

	Aetiologies	n (%)
Neurological (n=23)	CVA	16(32%)
	Haemorrhagic	6(12%)
	Non haemorrhagic	10 (20%)
	Seizures	4 (8%)
	Meningitis	3 (6%)
Non-Neurological (n=27)	Hepatic encephalopathy	9 (18%)
	Uremic encephalopathy	4(8%)
	Sepsis	4(8%)
	Hypoglycaemia	3(6%)
	Hyponatremia	2(4%)
	Other	5(10%)

Table: 4 Length of ICU Stay

	Average LOS (days)
Duration of overall ICU stay	4.26
Duration of ICU stay in Non-neurological patients	2.86
Duration of ICU stay in Neurological patients	5.66

Table: 5 Disposition based on admission GCS Score

Disposition	GCS Score			Total
	<8	9-13	>13	
Ward	2	7	6	15
ICU	12	21	2	35
Total (n)	14	28	8	50
Chi-square : 9.69 ; p= 0.008				

Table: 6 Intubation rate among AMS patients

	Number of patients (%)
Overall intubation rate	16 (32%)
Intubation rate in non-neurological case	5 (10%)
Intubation rate in neurological case	11 (22%)

Discussion

Based on the findings of the current study, non-neurological conditions emerged as the predominant causes of altered sensorium, highlighting significant differences across age groups. Specifically, 58% of patients were aged over 60 years, while 42% were under 60 years old.

Comparing these results with previous studies, Mose CP et al. reported that 65.88% of patients were over 60 years old, indicating variability in age distribution across studies. Similarly, Nomula S. et al. also observed comparable trends to our findings. These discrepancies may stem from differences in inclusion criteria and demographic characteristics among different regions. While some authors have described a bimodal age distribution in altered sensorium cases, encompassing both young adults and the elderly, our study did not demonstrate a similar bimodal pattern.

In the present study, 62% of participants were male, while 38% were female. Similar gender distribution was noted by Cherukuri SK et al. [8]. Conversely, Mose CP et al. [11] reported a different distribution with 48% males and 52% females, a pattern also observed by Kanich et al. 3 and Xiao et al. [5].

Regarding disease categories, 46% of patients in our study had neurological diseases, with cerebral vascular accident (CVA) being the most common (32%). Non-neurological diseases accounted for 54% of cases, with hepatic encephalopathy being the most frequent (18%), consistent with findings from Mose CP et al. and Malapur S et al. [11,16]

In terms of Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) scores, 16% of patients had scores >13, 56% had scores between 9-13, and 28% had scores ≤8. Our study, similar to Mose CP et al. [11], found a significant

association between GCS score and ICU disposition, with lower scores more frequently leading to ICU admission. The overall mortality rate in our study was 38%, which contrasts sharply with the 8.4% reported by Sørensen et al.[17]. Regarding ICU stay duration and intubation rates, no comparative studies have been conducted with AMS patients to date, suggesting a potential new direction for future research using our study's database.

It's important to note that our findings may have limited external validity due to our study's small sample size and the diverse demographic profiles specific to our region.

Conclusion

Based on the data from our study, it is evident that altered sensorium can stem from a variety of distinct causes. We observed a higher incidence of altered mental status among older age groups and male patients. Non-neurological causes were more prevalent than primary neurological causes. Specifically, the most common cause of altered mental status identified in our study was cerebral vascular accident (CVA).

Study limitation

The study results may be influenced by limitations such as a small sample size and the single-centre nature of the study. Therefore, larger-scale prospective studies are necessary to comprehensively evaluate patients presenting with acute altered mental status and to effectively manage mortality in the Emergency Department.

Author contributions

- Participated in research design
- Participated in the writing of the paper
- Participated in the performance of the research
- Participated in data analysis

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